

Project CHANGES – Spoke 4

D12 – Implementation of pilot and research studies

– Type B – v1.0

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1. Introduction

Within the research lines of Spoke 4, one of our main goals is to experiment with the use of virtual (energy-efficient) technologies within defined and representative real-case scenarios. In particular, we aim to experiment with them using different museum and art collection templates to design specific case studies, deriving and applying best practices that can be further adapted and reused in institutions and contexts with similar characteristics. The six templates of museums and art collections identified are described as follows:

- Type A – high-density and innovative museum;
- Type B – natural history and scientific museum;
- Type C – widespread art gallery;
- Type D – sites museums with tangible and intangible heritage and landscapes, among those that have either low or no virtual and digital implementations with a particular focus in southern Italy;
- Type E – historical palaces, labelled as museums, among the most important in the Italian heritage context, including UNESCO sites;
- Type F – demo-ethnic-anthropological museums, including rural culture museums (with less than 20,000 visitors per year), anthropological museums and museums of art and popular traditions.

In this deliverable, we describe the outcomes of the work conducted with the cultural heritage institutions we have contacted that are compliant with Type B, with whom we have established collaborative research projects. In particular, we have identified a set of cultural institutions with which we have set up specific research projects to put into practice existing and ad-hoc tools developed to provide a system to be freely reusable in a similar context by other cultural institutions not necessarily involved in the project.

Some of these projects, referred to as “core” case studies, have been conducted in collaboration with companies that provide implementation efforts and institutions that offer domain-specific cultural knowledge and citizen engagement. The companies involved were selected through a public call for applications, supported by the project's funds (i.e., cascade calls). These “core” case studies have also been accompanied by additional *research case studies* aligned with the project templates and goals, which the partners of Spoke 4 have used to experiment with further adoptions of the aforementioned workflow, methodologies and tools within the project's period.

2. "Core" case studies

2.1. PALEOTWIN: Virtual Technologies at the service of the "Giovanni Capellini Museum" Geology Collection

Outline clear goals and objectives

Describe the initial situation

The Collezione di Geologia "Museo Giovanni Capellini" is a paleontological and geological museum established in 1881, although the oldest collections date back to the XVI century. The museum is hosted in an historical building that has been modified and renovated several times, the last one in 1960. This last refurbishment, especially, has saved all the original XIX cabinets, but it has half-sized the space available, leaving the specimens very crowded and difficult to comprehend for the modern public.

Describe the chosen technologies to be implemented

The project includes four different levels: 1.The developing of a management software and server able to run several different hardware for output contents. 2.The creation of four avatars of the past museum directors who will talk about their idea of the museum and their idea of geology as a science. 3.Two immersive rooms where the software enables the curator to construct temporary exhibitions based on digital models. 4.An augmented reality itinerary between the historical cabinets of the first floor.

Identify specific challenges and opportunities

The main challenge has been to coordinate the work and schedule of the many stakeholders involved. In particular, the companies working methods and schedules do not always assimilate with university, where the lack of resources dedicated to the project is a major obstacle. The need to have a complete open access output has also been an issue when dealing with private companies, and the planning had to be revised several times.

On the other hand, the opportunity to work with different people, coming from with different backgrounds have enhanced the knowledge of the museum staff, and it has been an opportunity to tackle problems from different point of views and acquire a range of possible solutions.

Consider the potential effects on the involved stakeholders (e.g., museums, local public bodies)

The aim of the project is to create an integrated system for digital exhibitions designed for museums, independently from their size, the aim is to allow each

institution to create their own exhibition in relation to their specific budget and possibilities. On the other side, the intent is to involve the public, creating multisensory exhibitions that could produce a new motivation to visit a museum for people who usually do not do so. The basic idea is to renovate an ancient museum without renovating, or rather give the public an alternative, and modern, option to get inspired and increase their knowledge on the modern and ancient world and the connection between the two.

Describe knowledge sharing among project participants

Illustrate the training activities for the staff of the winning companies (e.g., seminars, workshops)

The geographical distance from the winning company headquarters have prevented in person meeting and all the activities have been performed online. Only a representative of one of the partner companies made a couple of onsite surveys.

Meetings have been organized to illustrate the museum history and background, the need for renovations and the museum needs and expectations regarding to the project.

Explain the exchange of knowledge by the winning companies regarding how the chosen technologies work and how to use them

The companies have explained the technical choices made in relation to the software architecture, especially about the need to adopt opensource software and the limitation that this choice involves. Due to initial misunderstanding some software features at first promised by the winning companies had to be abandoned, as they did not meet the opensource requirements.

Once this technical issue has been solved, the company shared their choices and explained to museums staff the software architecture and how the different component relate to each other's. Nevertheless, as none of the museum staff is a trained informatic no code, nor deep technical details have been shared.

Describe how the guidelines and prototypes identified (in WP3) have been used (or not)

Detail the digitalisation processes

Digitization processes have been performed by University of Bologna and CNR staff following the guidelines identified in WP3: a selection of fossil specimens and plasters have been chosen to be digitized using several techniques (e.g. photogrammetry, laser

scanners and 360 cameras), the outputs comprehend a raw digital twin of the object DCHO and an optimized version of the same DCHO.

Illustrate User interface (UI) and user experience (UX) design

User interface has been designed in order to be as easy to use as possible, the museum staff that will manage the software has no specific training in informatic and UI interface should be sufficiently straightforward. The database can be filled importing excel data from external databases to minimize filling errors and the exhibit configurator has been developed with an intuitive drag and drop design.

The user experience too has been designed to be as intuitive as possible, 3D objects are displayed using ATON framework that automatically adapts to different devices layouts. Two different exhibit experiences have been developed: one for children and one for "standard" users, all accessible by icons on the touchscreen devices. An engaging interface has been designed, although lack of time has prevented some refinements. Onsite users will be able to interact with touchscreen devices (32" and 75" monitors) and conversational avatars, moreover they will be able to access to AR contents via their mobile phone, both onsite and from home.

Outline software programming design

The software is a central repository for the management and retrieval of digital material, it supports various digital formats (e.g. .txt, .avi, .mp3, .mp4, .gltf). Is designed as an intranet network where hardware and software components work together to provide configuration, data management and advanced visualization (AR, VR and avatars).

The software uses http communication protocols within the client, rest API and the servers, it uses standard routes including get, post, put, delete. The server has a dual network card: one managing the LAN local network where all the museum devices are connected, one managing the WLAN network with request from user's mobile phones. Security protocols have also been implemented using BearerToken with JSON Web Token used in a Node.js web app, to authorize requests between client and server.

Mongo DB Community Edition is a free NoSQL database which has been chosen at it is flexible and it well fit the project requirements, all information within the database are stored in JSON formats.

Pinpoint what has not been used and explain why

We abandoned the initial idea of "real" conversational avatars able to answer hypothetically all visitor questions, as the technology required to develop them is non-opensource and did not meet the project requirements.

Outline the introduction of the technology to museum staff or other involved stakeholders (e.g., local public bodies, tour guides)

Training on use and maintenance

One day of training on software and server use for the museum staff and the devices set-up in the museum has been performed by the winning company. Moreover, a user manual with detailed information on usage and software features will be released.

Describe opportunities and objectives

The software is designed to be easy to use even for users with no training in informatics and programming. The goal is that museum curators will be able to manage their collection and set temporary exhibitions with the lowest effort possible. Also, curators should be able to grant access to the system to on term personnel, depending on the specific need of the museums.

Familiarise staff with technology through training sessions and workshops on self-guided learning

Training of new staff is supposed to be a straightforward process and can be done either onsite, or remotely via published manuals, or recorded tutorial videos.

Collect staff feedback

As the companies have sent all the hardware and software material right at the end of the project deadline, it was not possible to collect staff feedback on the software usage, the museum staff still need to complete the training.

Describe the experimentation session

Evaluate with real users to track of the effectiveness and appropriateness of the proposed solutions

Due to the delay of museum refurbishment, the rooms that were supposed to host the new exhibit that will utilize the software developed in the project, will be ready only in November 2025. The new exhibition is supposed to open on December the 12th, thus no evaluation on real users have been possible so far. Nevertheless, the software has been implemented to collect data log of chosen KPI, we thus plan to have the first data on costumers by the end of December 2025.

Identify strengths and weaknesses (possibly using a SWOT analysis)

STRENGTHS	WEAKNESS
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<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Software flexibility and adaptability to different context and topics. - Easy to use, easy to maintain 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Potential software instability. - Limited time (if any) available for testing onsite. - Need of IT support for future OS updates;
OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Combines digital exhibitions in a physical space with resources available on the web. - Attract teenagers and other usually non-interested publics into museums 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of staff resource allocated to maintenance - Technology gap that might need consistent software updates - Technological solutions that age quickly

Explain how the proposed solutions can foster citizens participation, accessibility, and social inclusion

The whole system, software and physical devices installed in the museum, have been designed to be inclusive:

- The 75" monitors have been mounted at a height accessible to people in wheelchairs and all the icons in the monitors will be accessible to all.
- Two different exhibition itineraries have been developed: one for children and one for standard adult users.
- Digital games, including one that can be activated with the use of 3D printed replicas of the museum objects, have been implemented for the youngsters, targeting children from 8 years old, up to teenagers.
- All the devices have the possibility to activate a vocal reader for people with visual disabilities.

Conclusions

Identify technological gaps

The software developed in the project is planned to be fairly simple and not too futuristic as it has to be used in museum which are most likely not too technologic, nor can access very onerous technologies. For this reason we planned solutions that are compatible with affordable devices on the market.

On the other hand, output such as avatars which have been animated using AI are "old" as soon as finished, as this learning technology is improving continuously.

Describe any unforeseen issues that arose during the implementation

Firstly, the initial user interface graphic proposed was way too basic, some improvements have been done, but the limited time available prevented further enhancements. Secondly, the AR models in the museum were supposed to be triggered with a QR code, and visible on the mobile screen while the user changed orientation. Unfortunately, such technology could not be implemented opensource in time and, as a result, the QR code are working, but when the mobile camera loses the QR the AR model disappears from the screen.

Delineate further lines of research

The software can be implemented with a better user interface, and a possible new research line can include the development of a travelling exhibition that involves multiple institutions and which integrate physical and digital objects that can travel virtually everywhere with different easy to set-up configurations, all managed by the same server.

2.2. CHAMELEON: Open. Connected. Accessible | Digitization and enhancement of museum environments and collections through enriched three-dimensional models

Outline clear goals and objectives

The CHAMELEON project (Reggia di Caserta - 3D Digital Twin) responds to the call for proposal of Spoke 4 - Virtual Technologies for Museums and Art Collections under the extended PNRR partnership CHANGES: Cultural Heritage Innovation for Next-Gen Sustainable Society (PE00000020), addressing topic number 7, "Open. Connected. Accessible | Digitisation and enhancement of museum environments and collections through enriched three-dimensional models".

CHAMELEON aims to develop digital tools for documenting, enhancing, sharing and narrating museum heritage, with a particular focus on science and natural history museums. The project focuses on one of the case studies identified as "core" for its importance within palaeontological and anthropological collections: the Piero Leonardi Museum of Palaeontology and Prehistory, part of the University of Ferrara's Museum System (hence SMA). Since 2013, the Museum has launched a digitisation campaign experimenting with different ways of acquiring the collections to create educational pathways and modernise exhibition content. Digitisation was mainly

aimed at non-displayed and medium-sized exhibits, leaving out more composite specimens such as complete large vertebrate skeletons and complex fossils.

CHAMELEON's main objectives are based on the use of digital tools to enhance the museum and its collection, addressing different needs and users. The first objective is to increase accessibility and knowledge (both onsite and remotely), maximising the openness to the general public. The project will also enable the museum's managers and curators to update the information system related to the fossil collections and to create adaptable visits and exhibitions. In order to achieve these goals, the project started with the accurate digital acquisitions of more than 30 objects selected on the basis of a preliminary educational and communicative design of the Museum. The palaeontological remains were carefully selected, taking into account their state of preservation, their scientific relevance and representativeness, as well as the need to link them to an augmented set of information.

The survey, carried out using a handheld structured-light 3D scanner and digital photogrammetry, is the result of a methodological assessment that highlights the critical interpretation and documentation possibilities offered by digitisation. The collaboration of the two Departments of Architecture and Humanities and the Piero Leonardi Museum of Palaeontology and Prehistory of the University of Ferrara, together with the technical partner Inception has been crucial in this respect. In fact, the aim is indeed to obtain semantically enriched 3D models, enhancing the levels of information linked to the metric-morphological data, according to current standards and Open Data, pursuing inclusion and accessibility.

The application design and development, led by technical partner MediaSoft, includes a back-end configuration module that allows exhibitors to define the content and behaviour of both the visitor experience and the virtual experience. MediaSoft is also designing and developing the Digital Asset Management module, Augmented Reality (AR) applications, and the scalable local cloud infrastructure hosting the entire system. The software platform is based on responsive design, standard metadata, and open APIs. The user experience design, by No Real Interactive, is embedded in the IT architecture of applications, and includes five main tools: Semantic XR Museum, Semantic XR Avatar, 360° AR Experiences, frontside AR Experiences, and Virtual Reality (VR) Experiences in specific settings. The overall outcome is a "chameleonic" repository able to manage online all the multimedia contents associated with the fruition and storytelling of tangible and intangible information. Dynamic digital paths are based on semantic associations and can be reconfigured by the end user, increasing engagement and interactivity with the Museum heritage. The repository is accessible from different interfaces to allow multiple digital fruitions, and applications are adaptable and integrable, exploiting the potential of virtual paths to create new forms of knowledge narration and to broaden critical-interpretative analyses of cultural heritage.

The Museum context

The context of the CHAMELON project is the Piero Leonardi Museum of Palaeontology and Prehistory (hence MPPPL). It is part of the SMA of the University of Ferrara, founded in 2007, which brings together the University's museums and historical-scientific collections. It is located at Palazzo Turchi di Bagno (Fig. 2.2.1), which houses the MPPPL, the Exhibition Hall, and the Botanical Garden and Herbarium. It also includes the "Giovanni Tumiatì" Anatomical Museum, and the scientific collections of historical interest located in the Departments (CISFIS and the Ancient Navarra Pharmacy). The richness of the SMA represents a great potential as it is an archive of knowledge and historical-naturalistic evidence to be exploited. This heritage, spread over several historic-architectural sites and only partially accessible today, fits well into an overall project of new and renewed accessibility of exhibition spaces and collections.

Figure 2.2.1. Main facade of Palazzo Turchi di Bagno, entrance to the Piero Leonardi Museum of Palaeontology and Prehistory.

The MPPPL was founded in 1964 by Professor Piero Leonardi, the first Chair of Geology at the University of Ferrara. The materials that make up the museum are the result of an intense activity of collection, acquisition and exchange that has continued over time. In addition, staff and students brought rocks and fossils to the Institute on every excursion and their return from conferences. Professor Leonardi himself donated his private collection to the museum when he retired. The exhibition section is entirely

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housed in the rooms of the piano nobile of the Palazzo Turchi di Bagno, along Corso Ercole I d'Este. The exhibition is divided into four main sections: Palaeontology of Vertebrates (Fig. 2.2.2), Human Palaeontology and Prehistory (Fig. 2.2.3), Palaeontology of Invertebrates, and Historical Geology.

The initial exhibition was mainly intended for university teaching, but since the late 1970s, the growing interest in natural sciences in compulsory education has led to a constant and increasing demand for the use of the museum. The building is currently used by the staff of the University of Ferrara and for temporary exhibitions on the ground floor, while the permanent exhibition is temporarily closed to the public, following the earthquakes that hit Emilia in 2012. However, it is possible to study the museum's collections by appointment or visit the exhibition rooms for small groups.

Figure 2.2.2. View of the room housing the Vertebrate Palaeontology section.

Figure 2.2.3. View of the room showing the Human Palaeontology and Prehistory section.

As a result, the museum has had to rely heavily on digital strategies. These current limitations on the permanent exhibition accessibility make it even more relevant to design a digital repository enhancing the collection through a reorganisation of the information and documentary sources and creating a set of digital interfaces for different uses, associating in-depth information content with the digital replicas of the exhibits.

The objectives of the core case study on the SMA Leonardi Museum are multiple, and can be summarised as follows:

- To increase accessibility (physical and virtual) through virtual routes, maximising openness to the public for different users through an inclusive approach;
- To activate a 3D digitisation process systematising what already digitised and focusing on exhibition and critical-interpretative opportunities that digitisation can offer;
- To apply a semantic approach to the models, enriching the levels of information associated with the metric-morphological data, according to current standards and with a view to Open Data / Semantic Web;

- To set up a platform and related VR and AR applications to make museum contents explorable;
- To activate a network with other Museum Systems or places of interest (e.g. archaeological excavations) for digital content sharing;
- To update the ICCD catalogue, in line with the ArCo project, and the Italian Ministry of Culture (MiC) Digital Library, including 3D and 4D (spatial-temporal) models.

Describe knowledge sharing among project participants

The knowledge-sharing process among the project participants - UNIFE (the research leader partner, as a joint cooperation among the Department of Architecture and the Department of Humanities), Inception and MediaSoft (the two involved companies) and the University of Ferrara's Museum System SMA (the cultural heritage partner) - has been structured to ensure effective communication, alignment of goals, and mutual learning throughout the project's lifecycle.

Project activities began immediately after the project approval decree was issued (public notice for the selection of project proposals - CUP J33C22002850006 - of 16 May 2024).

The project kick-off meeting was held on 25 June 2024, in order to set immediately the overall methodological approach and to share the guidelines outlined by Spoke 4. This was followed by regular joint meetings between all partners on the general progress of the project and one-to-one meetings between the partners involved in specific activities.

While internal meetings between staff from the Department of Architecture and staff from the Department of Humanities at the University of Ferrara together with the SMA personnel were held at least weekly, meetings with partner companies were scheduled, after the start-up phase in June, on the basis of the specific tasks assigned. Regular plenary calls were indeed a very effective way for the work alignment. Between June and December 2024, 13 plenary meetings were held organized by UNIFE. A specific meeting was organised with Spoke 4 staff (on 23 July 2024) in order to align on technical aspects of the project's development and sharing guidelines related to acquisition, processing, and Web3D publication of project data. Between January and September 2022, 12 plenary meetings were held.

In addition to online meetings, several site visits were made to the Museum, and much of the work was carried out directly within the Museum areas and rooms, including supporting activities by research fellows recruited as part of the project to carry out specific activities such as consulting and digitising archive documents.

During the different digitisation sessions carried out by Inception, the Museum staff had the opportunity to learn about the different technologies used for 3D object acquisition and received training on the overall workflow, supporting the project's broader objectives.

The SMA personnel shared essential knowledge and information related to the Museum collections, on which building up the applications and storytelling.

Describe how the guidelines and prototypes identified (in WP3) have been used (or not)

The development of the project action related to the digitisation of museum exhibits to obtain 3D models was anticipated by a careful analysis of the methodological approach and semantic mapping for the enrichment of models with information content. The careful analysis of the needs for narration through digital applications was developed according to the semantic-informative approach, while semantic mapping allowed the preparation of models for information enrichment.

The first phase involved the analysis of the museum context, both in terms of the characteristics of the exhibition halls and of the displayed objects. The University of Ferrara, through the joint work of the two departments (Architecture and Humanities), developed the overall methodological framework, defining the objectives for the different users and analysing the best reference practices. The joint work between the partners made it possible to define survey methodologies, enhancing the museum's needs.

The selection of exhibits to be digitised was guided by criteria of scientific, historical and narrative relevance, in line with the project's objectives. Firstly, specimens of central importance to the museum were selected as representatives of a collection able to tell the story of the area studied and its natural context. Secondly, special attention was paid to specimens with taphonomic characteristics and fossilisation or conservation processes of exceptional interest, which offer an important opportunity for study and valorisation through digitisation. The selection was also guided by the narrative purpose of the project: the specimens were identified to reconstruct significant thematic environments, such as the landscape of Settepolesini or deep-sea ecosystems, in order to create immersive and informative paths that make complex and scientifically relevant content accessible to the public. More than 30 specimens have been collected according to these criteria, with the possibility of adding other objects from the collection to the Museum's digital assets in the future.

The digital acquisition of the specimens (34 objects) focused on the most representative and relevant items. The use of advanced digitisation techniques made it possible to fulfil the need for high-quality and accurate 3D models, but also to open

up new interpretative and documentation opportunities, enriching the information levels associated with each object. Two three-dimensional survey methods were selected: structured light scanning and photogrammetry.

The handheld structured light scanner, which uses projections of light patterns onto the surface to be scanned, is a 3D scanning technology that combines the principle of triangulation with light projection, allowing precise and detailed measurement of surfaces. It is therefore particularly effective in gathering qualitative and quantitative information about the geometry of the object, making it ideal for surveying complex shapes. The decision to use a handheld scanner, i.e. a portable scanner, lies precisely in its mobility, which allows the operator to move freely around the object to be scanned, unlike fixed scanners that require a stable support. In addition to ease of use and, consequently, reduced scanning times, its freedom of movement offers greater possibilities for detecting objects that, due to their size or fragility, cannot be moved from their original location.

The laser scanner used is the Einscan PRO HD with 0.2 mm resolution. The surveyed objects were scanned by rotating the instrument around them, starting from the front and proceeding to the back, when possible (Fig. 2.2.4). Afterwards, with the use of the EXscan software, a complete textured model was processed using the scanner's onboard camera. The final result was an .OBJ file with textures in .JPEG format.

Despite the freedom of movement given by its portability, the use of the laser scanner was not very effective for some artefacts due to the small size of the object combined with the very complex geometric characteristics. For this reason, and to capture textures as best as possible, the digital photogrammetry (or Structure from Motion - SfM) was chosen for a set of objects. Photogrammetry is a surveying technique based on the analysis of photographs taken from different angles, which is significant in capturing information on the colours and textures of surfaces, which can be used to improve the visual appearance of 3D models.

Figure 2.2.4. 3D survey phases by structured light laser scanner.

Although laser scanner surveying can provide much higher accuracy in terms of geometry and a higher point density, photogrammetry has the advantage that the camera can be moved more freely and does not necessarily require the use of a fixed support. The camera used for photogrammetry is the Sony A7 r5 full frame 60 megapixel model with fixed 50mm macro lens and ring flash. The objects to be surveyed were photographed starting from the front and progressing with several shots along the main axes, thus making a rotating movement with the camera around the object (Fig. 2.2.5).

Figure 2.2.5. Views of the set for photogrammetric survey.

Figure 2.2.6. Steps in the processing of the 3D model of the Deinotherium (on the left). Top, solid model, above, textured model. On the right, Sicilian elephant 3D model processing.

It was then possible to scale it using GCPs (Ground Control Points) of known coordinates. The four viewpoints - front, side and front - (two for objects with simpler geometry) made it possible to completely cover the surface of the object in order to obtain 3D models without gaps.

The controlled light of the flash and the fixed lighting set allowed the creation of a complete texture without chromatic aberrations (Fig. 2.2.6). The software used for the photogrammetric project is Agisoft Metashape with final outputs in .OBJ format and texture in .JPEG format.

The 3D digitisation through digital photogrammetry has been performed by arranging a specific set. Objects were placed on a support within a fixed lighting set. In order to obtain the complete digital object, some photos were taken by rotating around the object, placed on a target, allowing easier recognition and merging of the different parts of the object during the data.

Wherever possible, a combination of the two methods was chosen as the surveying method (Fig. 2.2.7), combining the geometric accuracy of the laser survey with the quality of the photogrammetric textures of the SfM models (Fig. 2.2.8- 2.2.9).

Figure 2.2.7. 3D model of the therapsid *Lystrosaurus*. On the left, the laser scanner model, on the right, the textured model.

Figure 2.2.8. Processing of the 3D textured model of the *Smilodon* via Metashape through 294 photos by a full-frame camera.

Figure 2.2.9. Above, development of the 3D model of the Smilodon by positioning the photos through tie points in Agisoft Metashape software. Below, wireframe model.

For each specimen selected for digitisation, a dedicated repository of cataloguing details has been created. Access to these datasheets integrates the digital enhancement of the museum's exhibit, allowing visitors to gain insights and more detailed information about the selected specimens.

Each datasheet has been divided into three macro-sections based on the nature and use of the specimens it contains:

SIGEC analytical fields, including the data reported in the SIGEC sheets of the specimens, together with the catalogue information.

Additional fields, including information such as the scientific name, informative texts, data on the characteristics of the fossil organism in life as reported in the scientific literature, the place where the specimen was recovered, the method of its acquisition by the MPPPL, and its location in the exhibition room.

Each specimen datasheet is also accompanied by a text transcribed into spoken audio for the visually impaired and neurodivergent people, using inclusive and accessible language. These texts have been written according to the principles of accessibility and inclusion, in particular by adopting the European "Easy-to-Read" guidelines to ensure that the information is easy to read and understand for all users.

Particular attention has been paid to linguistic clarity, readability (including for users with dyslexia), and the removal of cognitive barriers, aimed at enabling independent and equal access to the Museum's information content. The descriptions simplify complex concepts without compromising scientific accuracy, and include detailed accounts of the physical characteristics of the objects, their position within the exhibition space, and their historical and scientific significance. Although intended for a non-specialist public, these fields provide bibliographic references for academic users.

Functional fields and taxonomy, including the data useful for indexing the specimen in the database and in search engines.

This repository has a dual function: a purely cataloguing function for the museum's users, and a didactic function for visitors who are interested in more detailed information about the specimens on display.

The User Experience design process was divided into four main actions: application design, digital use design, inclusive use design, and gamified use design. The applications setting up started from the semantic mapping and identification of the objects to be digitised, describing the IT architecture (Fig. 2.2.10) for managing the flow of data to/from the central repository (e.g. client-server), defining the hardware required for the creation and use of the prototypes being developed, and considering the quantity and quality of the data to be managed.

Figure 2.2.10. CHAMELEON IT architecture.

The hardware included all identified devices that could be used by each target user. A major part was the design of the software 'layer' (middleware) to connect the repository with the application prototypes, and the design of a 'chameleon-like' repository, able to:

- manage online all the multimedia assets that can be associated with a tangible or intangible museum object, including 3D replicas, audio-video clips, dialogues with avatars, information for users with different types of disabilities, etc.;
- enable to design dynamic digital visitor paths, i.e. based on semantic associations configurable by museum curators (e.g. to support temporary physical exhibitions or to create temporary online virtual exhibitions);
- allow the reconfiguration of the created itineraries by the end users (oriented and facilitated action), in order to adapt visits and increase their involvement.

The aim is to create a single repository accessible from "n" interfaces, different in form and function, allowing multiple digital uses supported by semantics that can be reconfigured at will. Such a repository fully meets the need to include not only the fruition of 3D models but of any other multimedia asset; and to create WebXR applications for exhibited objects, as a container for the virtual replicas, and related data and metadata, accessible through effective interfaces in the exploration of the 3D models via web browser. The identification of target users (curator, general user, specific user, disabled user, etc.) and expectations from the proposed experiences, and the analysis of the User Journey led to development of the User Experience (UX), described by means of graphical schematisations highlighting possible actions,

criticalities (such as over-inoculation, loops, etc.), limits and freedoms granted to the user by correlating them with the combinatory potential offered by the "chameleon-like" repository.

The user interface is designed specifically for each prototype, including functionality, graphical appearance, multi-device responsiveness, and accessibility. The design of an inclusive digital use is necessary both when the digital is considered to support a visit to a real museum, and when the museum (with its multiple declinations) is virtual. The "chameleon-like" repository will also allow disadvantaged users to configure their own path. Considering the game as a mode of cultural access not exclusively for children, a specific task to plan how to introduce 'gamified' logics in the production of digital fruition paths was introduced. Starting from the analysis of gaming best practices for museum context (style, time, rewards, correlation with the objects on display, etc.), the aim is to describe at least a gamified application to be structured on the semantic repository and applied in the different prototypes. This task is also in line with the Spoke 4 partnership willingness to develop a gaming activity that includes all the core case studies.

The semantic repository allows the online management of all multimedia assets, the design of new experience paths by the curator, and their reconfigurability. It includes:

The "semantic editor", an intuitive configuration back-end based on a drag and drop interface that allows the curator to create experiences, and user interfaces. Content is managed by populating the repository.

The "Semantic XR Museum" prototype for browser-based use of digital experiences through the user's own device, remote use of AR and VR, generic, gamified and inclusive paths. In addition to applications for exploring object models with augmented content, two immersive environments are also included.

The "Semantic AR Collections" prototype enables the marker-based AR experience on the display case, which can be activated by QR code. This application is realised through the creation of thirty prehistoric animals.

The "Semantic XR Avatar" prototype enables the experience of dialogue with a conversational avatar that can be accessed via a web browser with a smartphone connected to the Internet.

Based on the requirements of the project, the infrastructure (system and physical) already available, and the goal of open-source, it was decided to implement a client-server infrastructure that does not rely on a cloud but on a single server installed locally and with the possibility of being reached from the outside through devices, applying secure and efficient communication protocols such as REST APIs, and open-source frameworks and libraries, to allow for future scalability. The choice was made to develop the applications in Node.js, taking advantage of its large community of

developers and its extensive open-source library. For authentication, the JWT Token authorisation protocol was chosen. The main components of the system infrastructure are the Frontend Configurator, i.e. the interface for the administrator user or designer who configures content and templates, which dialogues with the Backend Configurator to manage the data saved in the database and any connected devices through HTTP protocols for fast data transfers. The Database contains the configured data and makes it accessible to the backend, using a document database (such as MongoDB) for flexible management of multimedia data or configurations. The output devices are AR/VR visualisers for immersive experiences. The connection to the backend allows configurations or interactive settings to be uploaded for display in VR or AR viewers, while QR Codes enable fast interaction between mobile devices and the platform. In terms of visualisation, the VR visualiser is managed by an API backend via Aton, a framework for VR experiences, connected to 3D objects and advanced configurations; the AR visualiser is based on AR.js, a JavaScript framework accessible via browser and used on mobile devices for experiences connected to 3D objects or other configured content.

Within the scope of the project, it was decided to use a NoSQL database, which does not require a rigid schema like relational databases, allowing different types of data (structured, semi-structured and unstructured) to be managed in the same database. Document-based databases represent documents in JSON format. Each document can have different fields without the need for structural changes, data can be added or modified quickly, complex data can be represented and documents can be accessed and written quickly. Furthermore, the use of a NoSQL database offers advantages in the programming workflow, especially for applications that require scalability, flexibility and high performance. It can have a natural integration with REST APIs since the JSON format integrates directly with APIs and frameworks; it also provides a natural mapping of objects that, in applications, can be saved directly without complicated conversions. By filling in an Excel file containing information required to populate the database, the data can be automatically imported into the web application. The curator's configuration, to create and manage the museum exhibits, and the visualisations for visitors have been designed considering all relevant aspects for museum applications, including the use of Aton, an open source framework based on Node.js and Three.js designed, developed and co-ordinated by VHLab, CNR ISPC to create Web3D/WebXR apps interacting with cultural heritage objects and 3D scenes on the Web. Aton adopts a 'develop once, deploy everywhere' approach, requiring no installation for end users, with its front-end automatically adapting to the device (mobile, desktop/kiosk or immersive XR). This modular framework offers a simple yet powerful API to manipulate graphics, customise event management for rich interactions and much more, along with a scalable rendering system with responsive interfaces. Regarding the AR framework, considering the search for primarily open source solutions, it was decided to use the AR.js library,

which is particularly suitable for mobile devices and works on both desktops and smartphones.

Outline the introduction of the technology to museum staff or other involved stakeholders (e.g., local public bodies, tour guides)

The project activities enabled a mutual exchange of knowledge between the partners. The introduction of the adopted technologies to the museum staff (curators, managers, researchers) took place both during plenary meetings and through specific activities carried out at the museum (3D survey of fossils, digitisation of archive resources, etc.).

On 21 July 2025, specific testing of the prototypes of the applications developed was carried out (Fig. 2.2.11), involving the museum staff, research fellows (Department of Architecture), PhD students (Departments of Architecture, Archaeology, etc.), research grant holders, students, interns at the Leonardi Museum, curator of the Leonardi Museum, fixed-term researchers from the University of Ferrara. Tests were performed on the functionality and usability of the AR solution.

To all participants it was asked to fill in an entry questionnaire, and the Net Promoter Score and the User Experience Questionnaire (Short Form) were administrated.

Figure 2.2.11. On-site tests on prototypes and training to the Museum staff.

Describe the experimentation session

At the moment, the main limitation lies in the physical accessibility of the Museum (small groups can access the building) and the need to renovate some of the exhibition equipment, which could further enhance the visitor experience through the applications developed.

Conclusions

The expected impacts of the project concern, in particular, the increase of the knowledge of the important heritage preserved in the Leonardi Museum, the increase of the visibility of the collections both for scientists and for citizens, young people, schools, and the involvement of the widest number of categories of users. The applications will lead to a consequent increase in the number of physical visitors who

go to the museum spaces, also through the organisation of specific visits and special openings, with the possibility of using digital applications designed for greater "on-the-spot" fruition. Another important expected result concerns digital access to the museum's collections through digital storytelling paths. A key role is played by the increase in knowledge of the Ferrara SMA and its collections, a reorganisation of the preserved objects, the definition of a database consisting of a set of digitised objects, expandable and integrable, with semantic features to enrich the information level in addition to the geometric-formal data. It is therefore expected that the digital applications developed by the project will increase public participation, make the exhibition more visible and sustainable, encourage a critical approach to knowledge both by curators and experts who can use the scientific content, and by citizens and specific users such as young people, schools, scientists, etc., increasing accessibility, inclusiveness and participation. The creation of the repository of digital models and data configured to integrate different interfaces allows multiple digital uses supported by semantics that can be reconfigured at will, according to its adaptive nature and the creation of multiple user interfaces. The project is indeed designed to be shareable and replicable, providing for the systematisation of digital contents (3D models of objects, ICCD data sheets where available, internal database developed by the Department of Humanities on the information content of the objects preserved at the Leonardi Museum, etc.), and the use of open formats and open platforms/repositories, through a replicable workflow, optimised for natural history and scientific museums, providing a data aggregation tool for research/in-depth analysis that can constitute a best practice at national level, providing for the creation of a set of technologies reusable in similar contexts.

3. Research case studies

3.1. Palazzo Poggi Museum, such as the Institute of Sciences: the new permanent exhibition featuring virtual, multimedia, and historical elements

Outline clear goals and objectives

Describe the initial situation

Palazzo Poggi, designed by Pellegrino Tibaldi in the 16th century and located in the heart of Bologna's university district, became the seat of the University in 1803.

Today, its first floor hosts the Museum of Palazzo Poggi, home to the renowned collection of the Institute of Sciences and part of the University Museum System (SMA). The palace was acquired by the Senate of Bologna in 1711 to house the newly

established Institute, which was officially installed there in 1714 and remained active until 1799.

Until now, the museum has carried the name Poggi, in reference to Cardinal Giovanni Poggi, who commissioned the construction of the Renaissance palace in 1556. However, the name can be somewhat misleading in relation to the museum's actual contents, which are primarily centred on the scientific legacy of the Institute of Sciences established in the early 18th century.

It is this museum—with its rooms dedicated to geography and nautical science, military architecture, physics, natural history, chemistry, human anatomy and obstetrics, alongside the 16th-century Aldrovandi Museum—and its new permanent exhibition that forms the case study of this research and redevelopment project.

The new layout project arose from the need to provide a coherent narrative for the museum's collections, which were fragmented and difficult for the public to understand. Feedback from visitors showed great appreciation for the collections, but a widespread difficulty in understanding the common thread that links them. Each room, or small group of rooms, was perceived as a separate and unrelated entity. Therefore, it was decided to make explicit what links the rooms in a single narrative, namely the history of the Institute of Sciences and the scholars who played a leading role in it.

The reinstallation of the Museum of Palazzo Poggi is supported by PNRR funding under Spoke 4 of the CHANGES project (Cultural Heritage Active Innovation for Sustainable Society) and aims to enhance the accessibility and experiential potential of the museum through the integration of advanced technologies.

The museum visit, indeed, did not include multimedia supports and was not interactive or multisensory. It was only partially unidirectional, as the direction to take after Room 5 was unclear: This will be clear with the opening of a second door between Room 5 and Room 6 (see Fig. 3.1.1), allowing for a more orderly narrative and a smoother flow.

The need to make the museum narrative easily accessible certainly benefits from the use of digital technologies and audiovisual tools. These allow visitors to explore the history of individual objects and specific scientific discoveries in greater depth, without weighing down the historical and artistic narrative that the new project creates in a coherent manner throughout the rooms and collections.

Particular attention was paid to making the artistic component accessible, describing both the container and the content. This made it necessary to create two narrative lines, integrating them as much as possible. One tells the story of the frescoes that adorn the sixteenth-century rooms, and the other recounts what happened in those rooms since they housed the Institute of Sciences.

Figure 3.1.1. Floor plan presented by the architectural firm PANSTUDIO

Describe the chosen technologies to be implemented

The exhibition design includes the use of illuminated panels, screens featuring videos and animations – favoring annotated 3D models over simple 2D images – interactive models navigable via touchscreens, a dynamic lighting system, 3D-printed replicas of artifacts from other SMA museums, semantically enriched volumes, and immersive environments accessible via desktop and, in one case, virtual reality. These elements encompass digital objects such as 2D/3D models, multimedia content, extended reality (XR), and digital replicas, as well as advanced heritage lighting technologies designed to enhance the visitor experience and encourage deeper engagement.

In developing the case study, we sought to remain mindful of the wealth of high-quality resources already produced by research institutions and partners involved in CHANGES and other related projects. In line with the FAIR principles – Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable – we prioritized the adaptation and reuse of existing multimedia materials, wherever they were coherent with the overall narrative and design of the museum experience and its individual rooms.

When appropriate and effectively integrated, we opted to repurpose existing and tested content in its entirety. Notable examples include the Digital Twin of Aldrovandi, and the Codex Cospi 3D Scholarly Edition. We also leveraged existing 3D object acquisitions already made available to the museum, reintroducing them through a newly designed user experience (UX) and user interface (UI).

However, a significant part of the exhibition setup involves the creation of entirely new multimedia content from scratch. This aspect will be explored in more detail below.

Figure 3.1.2. Ceiling paintings – Room Two

One of the main technologies chosen for the project is WebAR—Augmented Reality, specifically to enhance the ceiling paintings with biblical and mythological themes. It operates directly through the smartphone's web browser, so that visitors simply scan a QR code with their own device, which leads them to a dedicated web page. There, using the device's camera, the fresco is recognized and "enhanced" with digital elements. No downloads are required: users only need an internet-connected smartphone with an up-to-date browser.

The system is based on an open-source library called MindAR.js, which enables image recognition (in this case, the fresco) and overlays multimedia content onto it. For the software to correctly identify the artworks, reference images must be created and

uploaded in advance. This is done using the official MindAR tool, the Image Target Compiler (<https://hiukim.github.io/mind-ar-js-doc/tools/compile>). By processing images of the frescoes through this tool, the system will be able to accurately recognize them during the visit and activate the associated digital content.

The user experience is designed to be intuitive:

- Upon entering the room, the visitor encounters a QR code that links to the AR web page.
- By then pointing their camera at each artwork, digital captions related to the piece will appear on the screen.
- This solution offers several advantages:
- User-friendly: it requires no downloads or installations, making it easy for visitors to use.
- Flexible and scalable: content can be updated or expanded at any time, with the possibility of adding new artworks or materials.
- Non-invasive: the solution does not alter the artwork or exhibition space, integrating naturally into the visitor experience.
- Low maintenance costs: there are no significant expenses involved in its upkeep.

As the entire system is built on freely available open-source web technologies, updates are fast and cost-effective, without requiring complex interventions on hardware or dedicated software.

Delving, then, into the details of selected rooms:

- Room 1
A large backlit panel introduces the Insignia of the Anziani Consoli, a rich collection of parchment documents produced between 1530 and 1796 and today preserved in the State Archives of Bologna. These insignia, originally bound into sixteen volumes, celebrated the city's governing magistrates and visually represent the institutional origins of the Institute of Sciences. To support visitor orientation within Palazzo Poggi, an interactive touchscreen table will also be installed at the center of the room.
- Room 2
A new layout for display cases and objects will be accompanied by a touchscreen presenting the Scholarly Digital edition of the Codex Cospi, ([P3D_I](#)) developed as part of Spoke 4 by Alice Bordignon and Davide Domenici, using the open-source PURE3D framework (developed by Maastricht University), which employs the VOYAGER viewer.

Figure 3.1.3. Scholarly Digital Edition of the Codex Cospici

Placed next to the original manuscript, the interface allows visitors to explore a detailed 3D model, including the normally hidden verso, and to navigate three thematic paths focusing on the manuscript's history, materials, and pigments. The edition is open-access and already available online, making it a reusable resource both during and after the visit.

In the same room, a second screen displays 3D models of three Aztec artifacts — a mask and two ceremonial knives — acquired together with the Codex Cospici. Digitized by Callieri and Cignoni for the ERIHS project and previously integrated into the Aldrovandi Digital Twin, these objects will be animated and recontextualized within the display.

- Room 6
This room focuses on the teaching innovations of Giovanni Antonio Galli, an 18th-century physician who recognized the importance of obstetrics well before it gained academic legitimacy. His goal was to expand physicians' anatomical knowledge and to train midwives to assist childbirth more safely and effectively. To this end, he created realistic clay models and invented the "birthing machine," a transparent womb used in practical demonstrations to guide students through delivery maneuvers.

Figure 3.1.4 Terracotta object depicting a 9-month twin pregnancy. On the left, the render of its digital replica to be 3D printed; on the right, the object placed inside a display case, protected by glass, in Room 6 of the Museum.

To enhance the tactile and experiential nature of this historical training, three objects from the original collection have been 3D scanned using a structured-light scanner (Artec Spider) and printed at 1:1 or slightly reduced scale. These models — depicting scenarios such as twin pregnancies or breech births — can be touched and explored directly by visitors.

- Room 10
Two lightboxes already owned by Palazzo Poggi will be reused. The current graphics will be replaced with images depicting Newton's experiments and related themes.
- Room 12
An animated video will be developed to illustrate Luigi Galvani's experiment, using original images from *De Viribus Electricitatis in Motu Musculari*. Artificial intelligence tools will be employed to generate short animated sequences based on these historical illustrations. These brief clips aim to enhance the public's understanding of the experimental procedures depicted in the original images. The process is currently in the testing phase, and the final AI platform to be used is still being evaluated.
- Room 13
Short video sequences will be extracted and re-edited from the film *Una Cattedra per Laura Bassi*. The clips will be used without sound and will primarily show the

scholar moving through the spaces of Palazzo Poggi.

In addition, three smaller (Fig. 3.1.1 – room 4, 9, 10), mostly currently unused rooms will be transformed into digital areas, featuring key artefacts and multimedia content linked to other collections within the University Museum System (SMA), including the Botanical Garden, "Luigi Cattaneo" Museum of Anatomical Wax Models and Specola Museum of Astrology.

- Room 4
This room features a touchscreen table positioned near the window, offering an interactive digital reproduction of Herbarium Vol. 2 by Ulisse Aldrovandi. The resource includes annotated Latin transcriptions and detailed plant classifications, presented in an page-flipping format, with semantic annotation. The digital content is stored locally on the computer, ensuring full functionality without requiring an internet connection.

Additionally, four selected plant specimens from Herbarium Vol. 2 have been reproduced as 3D embossed prints, providing visitors with a tactile experience of the botanical collection.

An existing display case houses four wooden tablets featuring woodblock prints of plant illustrations. A nearby table presents 3D printed replicas of these tablets, which were created for a previous project and are now reused here to offer visitors a tactile experience of the botanical prints.

- Room 9
A table displays three 3D printed models from the "Luigi Cattaneo" Museum of Anatomical Wax Models, illustrating acromegaly. The models include an acromegalic skull (resin), a normal skull (resin), and a half-bust of an acromegalic person (filament print). These objects were captured using scanning and photogrammetry techniques, adapted for 3D printing, and reproduced at a 1:1 scale in the room. The size difference in the skulls is particularly important for understanding the condition.

Figure 3.1.5. 3D render of two objects to be printed, acquired with an Artec Spider scanner and optimized at 0.3 mm resolution. The first two images (from left to right) show the digitalization of a skull with acromegaly, while the other two depict

a norm conformed skull.

Additionally, a touchscreen table offers a virtual reconstruction of the main hall of the Museum of Anatomical Wax models. Visitors can interact with and explore around ten 3D objects; some previously created for other projects and others newly acquired through recent scanning campaigns. The system runs locally on the PC, requiring no internet connection or external wiring.

- Room 11
A monitor will be available showing an introductory video about the Physics Collection and the Museo della Specola.

A dedicated room (Fig. 3.1.1- room 16) near the ticket office will be used to present and interact with the digital twin of temporary exposition of Ulisse Aldrovandi: The Other Renaissance (2022), which is subject of another case study under Spoke 4. Two 40-inch touchscreens will be available for exploring the Digital Twin. By appointment, visitors can experience the exhibition in virtual reality with the guidance of staff, using two or three Oculus headsets, allowing them to enjoy an immersive experience together.

Identify specific challenges and opportunities

The reinstallation presents both logistical and conceptual challenges, including the coordination of multiple stakeholders—from curators and technicians to digital content developers and university departments. One of the main opportunities lies in redefining the narrative structure of the museum to restore coherence and clarity, and to re-centre the museum around the legacy of the Institute of Sciences. The aim is to provide visitors with a more intelligible and meaningful experience of the Institute's pioneering role in introducing experimental science to Bologna and reforming the historic Studium.

The introductory room will offer an immersive account of the history of the palace, the figure of Luigi Ferdinando Marsili, and the intellectual atmosphere of 18th-century Bologna. The museum pathway will follow a chronological and thematic logic—from the 16th- and 17th-century collections of Aldrovandi and Cospi, to the naturalist atelier of Aldrovandi and the 1907 reconstruction of his historical museum. A re-opened historical doorway will lead into rooms dedicated to the School of Obstetrics and anatomical waxes by Lelli and the Morandi-Manzolini, then to the gallery on optics, light experiments, and figures such as Campani, Laura Bassi, and Luigi Galvani. A key priority is to remove incongruous additions and restore the integrity of the historic display cases.

Consider the potential effects on the involved stakeholders (e.g., museums, local public bodies)

The project offers wide-reaching benefits to a range of stakeholders. For the University Museum System (SMA), Palazzo Poggi will function as a central access point, encouraging cross-visits to other collections both physically and virtually. Local public bodies stand to benefit from an enhanced cultural destination that strengthens Bologna's identity as a city of science and knowledge. For the public, the museum promises a more engaging, accessible, and layered experience, where scientific content is presented in dialogue with art, architecture, and literature.

A parallel pathway, independent yet complementary to the main scientific route, will highlight the richly decorated interiors of the palace itself. This itinerary will emphasise the interplay between 16th-century visual culture and emerging scientific thought, shedding light on the original functions of the rooms and the symbolic value of their frescoes.

Of symbolic significance is the reopening of the passage through Aula Quarta, allowing direct access to the University Library. More than a physical connection, this restoration revives the historic link between the Institute of Sciences and the Library—strengthened in the 18th century by Pope Benedict XIV—positioning the museum as a unified centre of knowledge, where science, art, and books converge in an integrated cultural experience.

Describe knowledge sharing among project participants

Illustrate the training activities for the staff of the winning companies (e.g., seminars, workshops)

Training activities were carried out through a close collaborative process involving the staff of the Museo di Palazzo Poggi, the architectural firm PAN STUDIO, and the team of multimedia experts, such as the VIDI Lab of the University of Bologna, and FrameLab. From February to July, weekly meetings were held to define a project that would consider the museum's practical needs while designing a more engaging user experience using digital technologies. On-site inspections at the museum, meetings with the Superintendency, and guided visits by the digitisation teams to several of the SMA museums (e.g., the VIDI Lab at the Botanical Garden, the Museo delle Cere Anatomiche "L. Cattaneo", and FrameLab at the Museo della Specola) were conducted. These activities were fundamental in allowing the teams to gain a deep understanding of the collections and spaces before starting the design phase.

The teams also participated in the 3D acquisition campaigns of objects and environments, gaining hands-on experience with the digital capture of the museum's assets.

Describe how the guidelines and prototypes identified (in WP3) have been used (or not)

Within WP3, several action plans were identified—Remote Interaction, Serious Games, Virtual Tours 360, AR Storytelling and Virtual Museums, Smart Object prototyping, AR and Machine Learning for Art Collections—aimed at studying existing virtual technologies applicable to the museums and collections analyzed in WP2, whether in their final state (i.e. without enhancing collections capabilities) or still under development, and at selecting the most appropriate ones for the pilot studies (WP4).

Among these approaches, we chose to focus on AR, the use of 3D models both virtual and printed (also for accessibility purposes), and the creation of explorable virtual spaces. This decision stemmed both from the intention to build upon existing experiences and materials—such as the Digital Twin, Codex Cospi, and other already available 3D models—and from practical considerations of time and staff expertise. For instance, developing a Serious Game would have required specialists in gaming and game engineering, while a 360° tour would not have suited the physical exhibition design, which instead prioritized the in-depth storytelling of symbolic objects or underappreciated areas, such as ceiling paintings, capable of capturing visitors' attention and inspiring them to further explore the collections.

Outline the introduction of the technology to museum staff or other involved stakeholders (e.g., local public bodies, tour guides)

Training on use and maintenance

The technological solutions were designed as ready-to-use installations, specifically packaged to minimize the risk of technical issues or accidental alterations over time. Examples include MP4 animations and locally stored, navigable 3D models that can be accessed directly from the computer—thus, in some cases, eliminating the need for an internet connection.

Familiarise staff with technology through training sessions and workshops on self-guided learning

Knowledge exchange by the winning companies is planned through dedicated sessions aimed at explaining how to operate the digital applications developed, as well as how to guide users through the virtual tours. These training sessions will take place during the installation phase, once all virtual resources are available—scheduled for late November to December. The goal is to ensure that museum staff are fully equipped to activate and manage the new digital tools independently.

Describe the experimentation session

The proposed solutions will be evaluated with real users to assess their effectiveness and appropriateness, with an identification of strengths and weaknesses, possibly through a SWOT analysis. Particular attention will be given to their potential in fostering citizens' participation, accessibility, and social inclusion. Further testing activities are planned in the coming months, and their results will be included in the project's final deliverables.

Conclusions

Identify technological gaps

The researchers worked on accessibility in collaboration with museum staff, who have solid experience and specific training in this area. However, due to time constraints (the project was funded one year before their expiry date), it was not possible to proceed with the usual sharing of information with associations and experts, including those specialized in services for blind and visually impaired users.

To ensure full technological autonomy of the exhibition path, and in the absence of in-house technical staff, a fully local solution was implemented. All multimedia content—such as videos, animations, and interactive applications—is accessed locally via USB drives or through software frameworks installed directly on PCs. One such example is the use of Aton, which enables the exploration of Room 6, dedicated to the anatomical wax collection and the annotated volume of Herbarium No. 2.

Moreover, except for augmented reality experiences, the system does not rely on the museum's Wi-Fi network. This choice was made to prevent potential disruptions caused by signal fluctuations or network outages.

However, this also meant forgoing the integration of potentially valuable online resources. For instance, in the case of the browsable herbarium, the original idea was to create a single IIF-based resource that could serve both museum visitors and botanical researchers—who often request access to this material from the Botanical Garden for study purposes. Instead, the decision was made to develop two separate resources: one optimized for local, offline use within the museum, and another designed for online access, thus meeting the requirement to avoid internet dependency while still enabling in-depth exploration.

Delineate further lines of research

Future lines of research will include the active involvement of blind and visually impaired individuals already in the design and testing phases, with the aim of ensuring more inclusive and accessible experiences from the outset.

Another key objective is the completion of the exhibition redesign, which currently extends only to Area 16 and does not yet include Areas 14 and 15 (see Fig. 3.1.1), dedicated to the military and naval collections. Future developments will focus on integrating this section into the digital and multimedia pathway, addressing the specific challenges posed by the 3D acquisition of the interior spaces of the historical ship models.

3.2. Digital Twin Ulisse Aldrovandi

Outline clear goals and objectives

Describe the initial situation

The exhibition *The Other Renaissance: Ulisse Aldrovandi and the Wonders of the World* (<https://site.unibo.it/aldrovandi500/en/mostra-l-altro-rinascimento>) was held at the Palazzo Poggi Museum (Via Zamboni 33, Bologna, Italy) from December 2022 to May 2023. The museum is located within Palazzo Poggi, a 16th-century building originally constructed as the residence of the Poggi family. In 1711, the Bolognese Senate acquired the building and transformed it into the Institute of Science and the Arts. During the Napoleonic reforms, the University was moved to this site, and its original historical collections were dismantled and distributed across various specialist university departments and municipal museums. At the end of the 20th century, a cultural initiative involving restoration and reorganisation allowed the Aldrovandi collection to return to Palazzo Poggi.

Aldrovandi's work belongs to the period of "archaic globalisation", characterised by aspirations towards universal monarchy, the global dissemination of major religions, and a humoral or moral understanding of health, as Aldrovandi himself was a physician. This pre-colonial phase also saw intellectual contributions from regions not yet engaged in empire-building. Although his perspective reflected the biases of his time, Aldrovandi was primarily motivated by a genuine desire to explore and document the remarkable diversity of the natural world. The exhibition highlighted this theme, presenting Aldrovandi's work as a means of rediscovering an alternative vision of the relationships between humanity, nature and space, one rooted in the pursuit of knowledge rather than conquest.

The exhibition received an enthusiastic response from the public, attracting over 30,000 visitors. This strong interest prompted the curators to extend its duration. The display of these remarkable objects, together with the engaging narrative that guided

visitors through the origins of scientific inquiry, created a compelling and memorable experience. As a temporary exhibition, its closure was widely seen as a missed opportunity for the many other individuals, both citizens and scholars, who might have wished to explore it. This ongoing issue, shared by many temporary exhibitions worldwide, has prompted us to use it as a particularly fitting case to highlight this priority and explore possible solutions through virtual technologies. The creation of a digital version of the exhibition aims to broaden access to his enduring message of peaceful, curiosity-led enquiry, a spirit that continues to shape the global identity of the University of Bologna.

Describe the chosen technologies to be implemented

One of the main aims of the case study was to establish acquisition and digitisation guidelines applicable to the various partners involved in the project, including researchers, professionals, and external companies. Thus, the creation of the digital twin of Ulisse Aldrovandi's exhibition is designed to provide a shared experimental framework and a reference point for developing a clear and reproducible workflow for digitising 3D cultural heritage assets. The creation of the exhibition's digital version involved linking the digital twin to a set of digital assets—including 3D models and multimedia content—representing items from the collection. These assets were then organised and made accessible online through a variety of devices, ranging from desktop computers and smartphones to tablets and virtual reality headsets.

To facilitate the re-use of our workflow for creating virtual exhibitions in other contexts, both within and beyond Spoke 4, we prioritised the use of open tools and software to process, manipulate, and present the data collected using photogrammetry and structured-light scanner techniques, along with the metadata generated for each physical and digital object.

A range of open-source solutions was selected to cover, in principle, all stages of the digitisation workflow: some examples of open software include Gimp, Raw Therapee, Blender, Instant Meshes, XNormal, Materialize, CloudCompare, Meshlab. Where necessary, proprietary software was also employed (i.e. 3DF Zephyr and Metashape for data processing), though standard file formats were used whenever possible to avoid dependency on specific applications, according to the Spoke 4 Data Management Plan. For instance, we used standard formats for 3D models (such as glTF, GLB, OBJ, MTL, E57), images or textures (TIFF, PNG, JPG, RAW), video (MP4, MOV), and audio (MP3).

Particular emphasis was placed on the adoption of the glTF format for 3D models, due to its status as an open and interoperable standard designed for Web3D applications. In this context, to offer an interactive and web-based presentation layer to final users [ATON framework](#) was adopted. ATON is built on large open-source ecosystems such as [Three.js](#) and [Node.js](#) and solid web standards to provide accessible alternatives

for organisations, labs, researchers, developers, and museums looking to design and implement cross-device Web3D/WebXR applications specifically for the Cultural Heritage sector. The open-source cloud platform NextCloud (<https://nextcloud.com/>) was chosen for the data layer, enabling straightforward management by the team responsible for 3D modelling and content creation. To quantitatively analyse and visualise aggregated data, we used [MELODY](#), an online dashboarding system for creating web-ready data stories that leverage Linked Open Data. Finally, for the long-term preservation of the data, Zenodo was selected due to its strong alignment with Open Science principles, its widespread recognition among project partners, its institutional independence, and its ability to host a dedicated community for the CHANGES – Spoke 4 project.

Identify specific challenges and opportunities

The main challenges encountered during the digitisation of a temporary exhibition in a museum context were as follows:

Time: The time constraint is a direct consequence of the temporary nature of the exhibition. On one hand, the exhibition being open to the public limited acquisition activities to a single weekly closing day. On the other hand, some of the objects on display were on loan and did not belong to the permanent collection of Palazzo Poggi, meaning they had to be returned to their respective institutions at the end of the event. This required selecting a digitisation method that was not only capable of delivering high-quality results but also the most time-efficient.

Space: Museum exhibition spaces are not typically designed to accommodate simultaneous digitisation efforts by multiple research teams. This led to logistical difficulties such as a lack of electrical sockets and insufficient workspace. Many objects could not be handled or removed from their display cases, which further complicated the digitisation process.

Light: Low, non-adjustable lighting in museums, moreover mostly composed of hard sources like spotlights, is highly unsuitable for digitisation, especially photogrammetry. For movable objects, portable lighting helped address this, though setup was challenging due to previously mentioned logistical constraints. But for immovable objects, the only possibility was to mitigate such adversarial lighting conditions using diffusers, screens, and fill lights to soften harsh shadows and reduce contrast between lit and shaded areas.

Object characteristics: Another challenge related to the digitisation process was the nature and sheer variety of the objects themselves – their shape, size (particularly large-scale items), and most notably, the materials. Some materials were either non-cooperative or hybrid in nature; for instance, black, shiny, metallic or transparent

surfaces can interfere with the accuracy of scanning instruments, thereby affecting the quality of the final dataset.

Considering the challenges encountered, one of the main goals of this case study has been to establish a set of guidelines to support researchers and other members of the Spoke in designing effective cultural heritage digitisation processes. Before moving towards final solutions for the case studies, the creation of the digital twin of Ulisse Aldrovandi's exhibition was defined to serve as a common experimental ground for a multidisciplinary team. This scenario provided a baseline for developing approaches and methods related to the acquisition, processing, optimisation, metadata integration, and online publication of 3D assets.

Consider the potential effects on the involved stakeholders (e.g., museums, local public bodies)

Various international policies support the focus on the universal use of digital data. Specifically in the field of Cultural Heritage, both UNESCO and the EU have already issued clear guidelines to promote and enhance the digitisation of heritage. These guidelines address not only cataloguing systems but also different modes of access to heritage objects and sites (e.g., on-site or decentralised). However, within the Italian context, expert users often perceive Cultural Heritage as comprising both tangible and intangible artefacts. In particular, Italian legislation and widely adopted practices have historically concentrated on the use and treatment of material objects. To align with current European cultural heritage policies and guidelines, it is necessary to move beyond this traditional framework and make digital enhancement a permanent and widespread practice in museums and art collections.

Starting from the Aldrovandi's digital twin case study, the main objectives can be outlined as follows:

- From a dissemination perspective: to increase public engagement and improve heritage communication strategies; enhance and make exhibition potential more sustainable; broaden accessibility, inclusivity, critical thinking, participation, and enjoyment; and promote deeper knowledge, care, and management of objects in all their forms.
- From an implementation perspective: to produce a digital version of the physical exhibition experience, preserving its narrative component even after the exhibition has ended. In doing so, the digital assets generated from the physical display create a realistic and graphically accurate knowledge model, structured semantically and enriched with metadata. This model is made accessible online through various devices (computers, smartphones, tablets, and VR headsets).
- From a methodological perspective: the project served as common ground for a multidisciplinary team to identify technologies and consolidate solutions that can

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be reused across different contexts. These solutions are intended to support not only the research partners involved in the case studies, but also external stakeholders (such as researchers, professionals, and businesses) engaged in cultural heritage digitisation.

Describe knowledge sharing among project participants

Illustrate the training activities for the staff of the winning companies (e.g., seminars, workshops)

An online presentation was given to the participating companies on 20 December 2024 to share the guidelines developed for the digitisation of cultural heritage ([Bordignon et al., 2025](#)). On this occasion, the digitisation team responsible for drafting the document presented the workflow that was designed and refined within the context of the Aldrovandi pilot case. The presentation slides can be accessed via the following [link](#).

This aspect does not involve a transfer of new technologies from the research team to the partner companies. What the project contributed was a standardized and structured workflow: a methodological framework that, on one hand, guided the activities and, on the other, introduced constraints that helped ensure consistency, comparability, and overall coherence across the different contributions. This structured approach translated research into practice, reinforcing the technological capabilities already present within the companies and enhancing their ability to operate within a coherent and replicable system.

A Google Form was created during the presentation to collect questions and concerns from the participating companies.

Describe how the guidelines and prototypes identified (in WP3) have been used (or not)

Detail the digitalisation processes

In this context, a specific document has been produced, offering guidelines based on the methodology established through this pilot case ([Bordignon et al., 2025](#)). These are consistent with those provided by the Italian Ministry of Culture (MiC), though they are intended for dissemination rather than documentation purposes.

Illustrate User interface (UI) and user experience (UX) design

A fundamental part of the digital transformation process of the Ulisse Aldrovandi and the Wonders of the World exhibition was the design of the user interface (UI) and user

experience (UX), aimed at ensuring an accessible, inclusive, and intuitive navigation system for diverse audiences. The design process followed a user-centred methodology, using Figma as the primary tool for prototyping, collaborative design, and interface validation. Prototypes were iteratively developed and tested to meet accessibility standards. Key considerations included color contrast, font legibility, screen reader compatibility, and keyboard navigability. Tools such as the [WebAIM Contrast Checker](#) were employed to ensure compliance with WCAG accessibility criteria.

In parallel, static data visualizations were designed and prototyped to support the exhibition's conceptual and interpretive framework. These visualizations played a critical role in highlighting the complexity of the collection, mapping relationships among items by theme, type, or provenance and so on. To generate these outputs, the open-source tool RAWGraphs ([Mauri et al., 2017](#)) was used, enabling the creation of custom, expressive visual representations that aligned with the exhibition's scientific and curatorial logic.

Overall, the interface balances narrative clarity, inclusive access, and content richness, transforming the exhibition's curatorial goals into a compelling digital experience across multiple devices.

Outline software programming design

To render objects' metadata within a web-based ecosystem, we adopted MELODY, an existing open-source online dashboarding system designed for creating web-ready data stories based on Linked Open Data. MELODY's modular architecture, based on standard web technologies and widely adopted frameworks, facilitates extension and reuse across diverse contexts. Leveraging MELODY's design [documentation](#) and component structure, we developed a dedicated API that extends its core functionalities. The API was conceived to provide a lightweight, flexible service for rendering metadata both as enriched text and data visualizations, independent of a specific platform. Its software design closely follows MELODY's architecture, emphasizing modularity, RESTful principles, and a clear separation between data retrieval (via SPARQL queries) and presentation logic. The configuration JSON files used by the API reflect the outcomes of the interface design process described above:

- They define the SPARQL queries needed to fetch relevant data;
- They structure the curated text and metadata to display for each object;
- They configure the type and parameters of data visualizations.

The MELODY-based API has been successfully reused in two distinct contexts: 1) inside ATON to display on-demand enriched information and visualizations during the

exploration of the digital twin, and 2) inside the Aldrovandi's catalogue, to dynamically render object cards within a web interface that allows users to explore the full collection.

Pinpoint what has not been used and explain why

The implementation has adhered to the prototypes and the established guidelines identified in WP3, with no significant deviations observed.

Outline the introduction of the technology to museum staff or other involved stakeholders (e.g., local public bodies, tour guides)

Training on use and maintenance

No training has been proposed so far, since the final product is in its final stage of development. Appropriate training sessions will be run before installing it in Palazzo Poggi, before the end of the project set to end of February 2025.

Describe opportunities and objectives

The final product will become available in the Museums of Palazzo Poggi in December 2025 as the first fully-virtual digital twin of a temporary exhibition, thus allowing users to continue to visit the original settings and objects exposed. In addition, the digital twin will be also made freely available on the web to anyone who is interested, thus enabling people not having the possibility to go Bologna to admire the digital twin in its original spaces to have, anyway, the possibility to be involved in the exhibition narrative.

Familiarise staff with technology through training sessions and workshops on self-guided learning

The final training with the museum staff will be run in December 2025 and January 2026 to illustrate how to use the system and how to introduce it to the users.

Collect staff feedback

In the past months we have organised several sessions within the Museum of Palazzo Poggi and in other national and international events to gain useful feedback to improve the product. These sessions have been run in the following context:

- European Researchers' Night, editions 2024 and 2025
- Tourisma – Archaeology and Tourism Exhibition, 21–23 February 2025, Florence;
- Internal meeting with the University of Bologna governance held during 2025
- Conference "Digital Humanities 2025 - Accessibility & Citizenship"

- UnaHerDoc–Una Europa PhD Workshop
- Conference “Disuguaglianze e sostenibilità: l’impegno dell’Università in Emilia Romagna”
- Conference “Patrimonio Culturale al Futuro: sostenibilità sociale, innovazione tecnologica, trasformazione digitale”
- Digital Heritage Congress Expo, 8–12 September 2025, Siena.

Describe the experimentation session

Evaluate with real users to track of the effectiveness and appropriateness of the proposed solutions

The Digital Twin has not yet been subjected to dedicated experimental sessions; these will be carried out in the coming months and will be included in the project’s final deliverables. However, the demo has undergone several presentation settings with potential users, as listed above in point 4, which provided useful feedback for improving the product.

Explain how the proposed solutions can foster citizens participation, accessibility, and social inclusion

In terms of dissemination, the Aldrovandi Digital Twin can foster citizen participation, accessibility, and social inclusion by enabling remote access to an exhibition that is no longer physically available. In terms of documentation, it represents a unique example of virtually preserving a temporary exhibition and reconstructing the exhibition context in which all the objects were originally displayed together, also serving as a valuable resource for researchers.

Conclusions

Identify technological gaps

- Challenges arose from the use of open formats and open-source software, which in certain cases complicated the workflow and hindered the production of high-quality data.
- Difficulties in defining a data model that could both adequately incorporate the state of the art and respond to the specific needs of the case studies, while remaining sufficiently general to be reused in other digitisation projects involving museum collections.
- The inherent complexity of formalising unstructured or semi-structured data.

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- Data collection was conducted collaboratively via shared platforms, posing coordination and consistency challenges.
- The need to develop a semi-automated system for converting tabular data into RDF capable of handling the structural complexity and variability of the input datasets.

Describe any unforeseen issues that arose during the implementation

- Optimisation: An iterative methodological process was undertaken to optimise 3D content for high performance in a web-based context, enabling smooth real-time interaction. Numerous attempts were required from both the digitisation and development teams to ensure that the prototype functioned efficiently without compromising photorealism.
- Bug resolution in both the desktop and VR versions demanded multiple iterations to identify and implement appropriate solutions within the ATON development environment.
- Acquisition conditions were often suboptimal due to the absence of dedicated digitisation spaces in museums, non-adjustable lighting, and the necessity to scan objects exclusively on days when the hosting institutions were closed. These constraints occasionally resulted in incomplete datasets, particularly for reflective or structurally complex objects, leading to imperfect or problematic meshes. Operators had to carry out extensive manual corrections, relying on documentation materials as reference.
- The organisation and correct naming of such a large volume of data proved to be a significant challenge. It was particularly difficult to establish a naming convention that could encompass and unify all the digitised cases.
- Limitations in the technology initially chosen for metadata conversion to RDF required substantial extensions to support the complexity and specificities of the input datasets.
- Continuous adjustments to mapping rules were necessary to address emerging research questions throughout the process.
- The initial complexity of maintaining the custom-built conversion tool necessitated the development of external plugins to facilitate reuse by domain experts without a technical background.

Delineate further lines of research

- Reuse the digital objects produced to design new exhibitions and interactive pathways within museum settings.

- Develop an augmented reality version of the experience to be hosted within the same spaces where the temporary exhibition was held.
- Broaden the intended audience of the prototype to maximise its impact—transforming it not only into a tool for cultural heritage enhancement but also as a testbed for psychological experiments (as already piloted during the project), and for initiatives in the social support domain. The prototype can thus be conceptualised as a virtual simulation environment, adaptable to different disciplines and contexts, thereby amplifying its cultural and societal value.
- Develop, through LimeSurvey, questionnaires aimed at formalising domain knowledge and enabling the semi-automated generation of mapping rules for the conversion software. The structured output of these questionnaires will be converted into mapping rules via a dedicated plugin (Chad-ASK).

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